

ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECT OF LIQUIDITY, SALES GROWTH, AND TANGIBILITY ON CAPITAL STRUCTURE WITH COMPANY SIZE MODERATION IN THE INFRASTRUCTURE SECTOR LISTED ON THE INDONESIA STOCK EXCHANGE (IDX) FOR THE PERIOD 2021-2024

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ABSTRACT

This study examines and analyzes factors that influence capital structure in the form of liquidity, sales growth, and tangibility with moderation of company size in the infrastructure sector listed on the IDX for the period 2021-2024. The method used in this study is quantitative with secondary data obtained through the publication of company financial reports on the IDX website or the company's official website. This study was conducted using panel data regression analysis and Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) techniques to test the moderating relationship. The results show that liquidity has a negative effect on capital structure, while sales growth has a positive effect on capital structure. However, tangibility has no effect on capital structure. Furthermore, company size can only moderate tangibility on capital structure, while liquidity and sales growth cannot be moderated by company size. The implications of this study indicate the importance of liquidity management and cash flow stability in maintaining a company's capital structure and the utilization of fixed assets as collateral for companies, especially small-scale companies in obtaining debt.

Keywords: Capital Structure, Liquidity, Sales Growth, Tangibility, Company Size.

1. INTRODUCTION

Infrastructure development is one of the main pillars for driving economic growth and improving public welfare. Infrastructure covers various fields such as transportation, energy, telecommunications, clean water, and sanitation. Economic activity can increase significantly if all areas of infrastructure operate optimally. For example, good road conditions can reduce logistics costs, and adequate digital infrastructure can improve operational efficiency. In addition, infrastructure development is believed to boost the real sector, absorb labor, increase public and government consumption, and encourage productive activities (Nugraha et al., 2020).

In line with the main priorities of the government during the 2014-2024 administration, Indonesia has experienced massive development over the past 10 years. This development has been

driven by the implementation of National Strategic Projects

(PSN), which are the government's main initiative to accelerate infrastructure provision. National Strategic Projects (PSN) are projects that are strategic in nature in supporting growth and equitable development to create jobs and improve people's welfare. Through PSN, a project receives special privileges in licensing and non-licensing because it is considered strategic in realizing national growth and equitable development (Wardana, 2022).

In 2016, there were 20 completed projects with an investment value of 32.3 trillion, which continued to be followed by an increase in the number of realizations for the following years until 2024.

Figure 1. PSN project realization and investment value
Source: Data processed by the author (2025)

The data shows an increase in project realization over the last two years of the 2014-2024 administration. Although these figures illustrate the successful completion of national infrastructure projects, they also reflect the high financing requirements in the infrastructure sector, as funding must be prepared from the early stages by the implementing companies to cover their operational activities.

This high financing requirement is in line with the development targets set out in the 2020-2024 National Medium-Term Development Plan (RPJMN), in which the government predicts that the total funding requirement will reach IDR 6,445 trillion. This total funding requirement has increased significantly from the 2015-2019 RPJMN, which was around Rp4,796.2 trillion (KPBK Kemenkeu, n.d.). This increase demonstrates the government's commitment to accelerating infrastructure development as an effort to boost economic growth and regional equity. However, the government does not bear the entire burden of this enormous funding requirement, covering only 37% of the total, or Rp2,385 trillion. Therefore, there is a financing gap to meet the funding requirement. In this case, the government has responded to this issue with a Public-Private Partnership (PPP) scheme solution, which is regulated through Presidential Regulation No. 38 of 2015.

Based on data from the 2020-2024 National Medium-Term Development Plan (RPJMN), the largest contribution to funding came from business entities, with a nominal value of Rp2,707 trillion. Financing carried out by business entities in the KPBK scheme is a source of project financing that generally comes from debt and equity, with debt accounting for 70-80% of the total project (KPBK Kemenkeu, n.d.). Although the largest portion of funding comes from business entities, the phenomenon of dependence on debt financing does not only occur in private business entities, but also in state-owned enterprises. In 2021, there were eight construction issuers with fairly high debt ratios as measured by DER, including four SOE issuers such as WSKT at 5.75x, ADHI at 5.97x, WIKA at 2.73x, PP at 2.92x, and four private issuers, namely SSIA at 0.95x, JKON at 0.62x, TOTL at 1.32x, and the highest from ACST at 16.29x (Sandria, 2021). Then, utility issuers, namely LAPD, recorded liabilities of Rp266.9 billion in 2021 with negative equity of Rp170.5 billion, resulting in a negative DER (Putra, 2022).

Additionally, high DER levels were also recorded for telecommunications issuers in 2022, namely TOWR at 446.90%, TBIG at 345.97%, and CENT at 246.53% (Tim Riset CNBC, 2022).

Referring to the latest statistical data released by the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX), the infrastructure sector has a high dependence on debt financing, as reflected in 29 companies out of a total of 71 infrastructure companies having extreme DER values, both above 100% and negative, such as WSKT (1236%), CENT (671%), MTRA (-286%), LAPD (763%), PTDU (-2665%), and BTEL (-101%). A high DER indicates a company's dependence on high debt usage, which increases interest expenses and potentially suppresses profits. Conversely, a negative DER indicates that the company's accumulated losses exceed its equity, reflecting the company's financial difficulties and potential bankruptcy (Fernando, 2025).

Research conducted by Alaali (2025); Dewi & Fachrurrozie (2021); Pathak & Chandani (2023); Purba et al. (2020); Putri & Dwiarti (2024) shows that liquidity has a negative effect on capital structure. Research by Jorden et al. (2022) and Rani et al. (2020) shows positive results between liquidity and capital structure. However, this is contradicted by the results of studies conducted by Boumlik et al. (2025); Hidayat et al. (2024); Tasrim et al. (2024), which found that capital structure cannot be influenced by liquidity. The research by Gunarianto et al. (2023) states that sales growth has a negative effect on capital structure. Different results were found in the research by Cahya et al. (2021) and Pathak & Chandani (2023), which showed a positive relationship between sales growth and capital structure. However, studies conducted by A. M. Ahmed et al. (2024); I. E. Ahmed & Sabah (2021); Albart et al. (2020); Purba et al. (2020) show that sales growth does not affect capital structure. Further research on tangibility conducted by A. M. Ahmed et al. (2024); Pathak & Chandani (2023); Sutomo et al. (2020) shows a positive effect on capital structure. Meanwhile, research conducted by Dewi & Fachrurrozie (2021) and Uddin et al. (2022) shows a negative relationship between tangibility and capital structure. However, research conducted by I. E. Ahmed & Sabah (2021); Albart et al. (2020); Hidayat et al. (2024) shows no effect between tangibility and capital structure.

Then, this study adds the variable of company size as a moderator to determine the strength of the relationship between liquidity, sales growth, and tangibility on capital structure. Several studies show insignificant and inconsistent relationships, so a moderating variable is needed because moderating variables can change the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables (Hair, 2019). Company size is considered capable of moderating because large-scale companies have the opportunity to improve their capital structure (Gunardi et al., 2020). Large companies generally have good credibility with external parties, making access to external funding easier. In addition, large companies have a broader market share, enabling more stable cash flow, thereby supporting sufficient internal funds. Research conducted by Dewi & Fachrurrozie, (2021); Jorden et al. (2022); Mukaromah & Suwanti (2022); Fitriyanto & Haryono (2020); Gunardi et al. (2020) shows that company size can moderate the relationship between financial variables and capital structure.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

2.1. Trade Off Theory

The trade-off theory was first proposed by Modigliani and Miller in 1963, stating that a company's capital structure, namely the ratio of debt to equity, will reach an optimal point when the benefits and costs of using debt are balanced (Modigliani & Miller, 1963). In this theory, companies face a trade-off between tax shields and financial distress costs to achieve an optimal capital structure in a perfectly competitive market without asymmetric information, agency costs, and bankruptcy costs (Nguyen et al., 2020). Pathak & Chandani (2023) explain that a company's leverage level is the result of an exchange between the benefits and costs of issuing debt and the benefits of debt derived from interest tax shields.

This theory argues that companies will have higher financial risk when obtaining tax benefits from debt. Therefore, companies need to set a level of debt usage that allows financial obligations to be met without causing financial risk. In line with the phenomenon of PPP schemes in project financing, a high debt utilization ratio of 70-80% indicates that the capital structure is close to the optimal limit according to Trade Off Theory, where the benefits of taxation are almost equal to the risks and costs of financial difficulties due to additional debt. Therefore, companies need to reconsider increasing their debt levels in order to avoid the risk of bankruptcy.

2.2. Optimal Capital Structure

Brigham & Houston (2019) state that the optimal capital structure is a combination of debt and equity consisting of preferred stock and common equity that can maximize the intrinsic value of the company and minimize the Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC) or the weighted average of the company's cost of capital (Brigham & Houston, 2019). In this case, adding debt can lower the WACC value because debt interest is cheaper than equity costs. However, too high an increase causes an increase in debt and equity costs, which ultimately increases the WACC value and leads to the risk of bankruptcy, so management needs to adjust the funding composition to maintain capital cost efficiency.

2.3. Pecking Order Theory

The Pecking Order Theory was proposed by Myers in 1984, which states that companies prefer internal financing over external financing, as well as debt over equity when issuing securities. Internal financing comes from cash reserves or a portfolio of tradable securities, while securities in external financing are through hybrid securities such as convertible bonds (Myers, 1984). This is in line with Chaklader & Padmapriya (2021), which states that there is an order in financing decisions, prioritizing internal funds first, then debt, and equity issuance as the last resort. This shows that there is a predetermined order in choosing payment options based on the Pecking Order Theory. The sequence of payment options consists of internal financing, debt, and equity. The order of preference is influenced by the emergence of costs related to information asymmetry and adverse selection risk (Chalençon & Marion, 2021). Internal

financing is the first choice because it has no transaction costs and low information asymmetry costs. Therefore, internal financing is more preferred over external financing, which often involves significant transaction costs, especially with external equity (Boumlik et al., 2025).

2.4. Relationship Among Variables and Hypothesis Development

2.4.1 Liquidity on Capital Structure.

Liquidity indicates a company's ability to meet its short-term obligations through the utilization of its current assets. Companies with high liquidity tend to choose internal funds as their main source of financing because they have sufficient cash to pay off their debts (Putri & Dwiarti, 2024). This is in line with the Pecking Order Theory, which states that companies prefer internal financing over external financing. The results of studies conducted by Pathak & Chandani (2023); Alaali (2025); Putri & Dwiarti (2024) show a negative relationship between liquidity and capital structure. Based on this description, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1: Liquidity has a significant negative effect on capital structure.

2.4.2 Sales Growth on Capital Structure.

High sales growth drives high production pressure, so funding for operations will also increase. In line with the opinion of Imronudin et al. (2022), the increasingly high growth rate makes companies more dependent on external capital such as debt financing. In the context of Trade Off Theory, companies tend to increase the proportion of debt in their capital structure because they have the ability to generate cash flow from high sales, so that debt burdens can be overcome properly and they can benefit from tax savings without causing bankruptcy risks. The results of studies conducted by Cahya et al. (2021) and Pathak & Chandani (2023) show a positive relationship between sales growth and capital structure. Based on this description, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H2: Sales growth has a significant positive effect on capital structure.

2.4.3 Tangibility on Capital Structure.

According to Wirianata & Viriany (2025), fixed assets are used as collateral for external parties when companies experience financial difficulties and are unable to pay their obligations. Tangibility provides a sense of security for creditors and reduces risk for companies, because fixed assets can be used as collateral. Referring to Trade Off Theory, this condition encourages companies to increase their use of debt to the optimal point, where the benefits received are still greater than the risk of bankruptcy costs. Therefore, companies tend to use debt in their operational activities when tangibility is high. These results are supported by research by A. M. Ahmed et al. (2024) and Sutomo et al. (2020), which shows a positive influence of tangibility on capital structure. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H3: Tangibility has a significant positive effect on capital structure.

2.4.4 Firm Size Moderates the Relationship between Liquidity and Capital Structure.

Large companies usually have high liquidity, so they will prioritize internal sources of funds to finance their operations in

accordance with the Pecking Order Theory (Sucianti & Darmayanti, 2025). However, large companies reflect the total assets owned by the company and make it easier for companies to obtain external funds (Hutauruk, 2020). Large companies are considered more stable in generating profits and have a lower risk of loss, so they are considered more capable of balancing the tax benefits of using debt with the risk of financial difficulties in accordance with Trade Off Theory.

H4: Company size moderates the effect of sales liquidity on capital structure.

2.4.5 Firm Size Moderates the Relationship between Sales Growth and Capital Structure.

Large companies have a wider market share and can achieve high sales (Renalya & Purwasih, 2022). Imronudin et al. (2022) state that a high growth rate makes companies more dependent on external capital. High growth encourages companies to continue to expand and borrow funds from external parties to meet their funding needs (Gusfriyanto & Sihombing, 2024). Based on Trade Off Theory, large companies tend to be better at balancing the tax benefits of using debt with the costs of financial difficulties because large companies have lower risks and face fewer obstacles in obtaining bank loans due to their better risk diversification capabilities compared to small companies (Kedzior et al., 2020). Based on the above description, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H5: Company size moderates the effect of sales growth on capital structure.

2.5.6 Firm Size Moderates the Relationship between Tangibility and Capital Structure.

Company size is measured using total assets owned. Hutauruk (2020) states that large companies reflect the total assets owned by the company and make it easier for companies to obtain external funds. Company assets, especially physical assets, can be used as collateral for companies to obtain debt (A. M. Ahmed et al., 2024). The larger the size of the company and the assets it owns, the greater the possibility of the company obtaining external funds in the form of debt. Based on Trade Off Theory, large companies can better overcome the risk of financial difficulties because they have greater assets than small companies. Previous studies conducted by Fitriyanto & Haryono (2020); Gunardi et al. (2020); Mukaromah & Suwari (2022) show that company size can moderate the relationship between tangibility and capital structure. Based on this description, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H6: Company size moderates the effect of tangibility on capital structure.

Figure 2. Research conceptual framework

Source: Data processed by the author (2025)

3. RESEARCH MEHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study uses a quantitative research design to investigate the effect of Liquidity (X1), Sales Growth (X2), and Tangibility (X3) on Capital Structure (Y), with Firm Size (Z) as a moderating variable and Firm Age (C) as a control variable.

3.2 Population and Sample

The population in this study was all infrastructure sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX), while the research sample was obtained using nonprobability sampling with the purposive sampling method. In this study, the purposive sampling method used judgment sampling, which involves selecting sample data based on sources that meet the criteria.

Table 3.1 Research Sample Criteria

No.	Description	total
Population: Infrastructure companies listed on the IDX		71
1.	Infrastructure companies not listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the period 2021-2024.	(9)
2.	Infrastructure companies not listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the period 2021-2024.	(2)
3.	Companies that did not publish complete annual financial reports for the 2021-2024 period.	(6)
Research Sample		54
Total observations (n x research period) (54 x 4)		216

Source: Data processed by the author (2025)

3.3 Data Collection

This study uses secondary data sourced from companies' financial statements and annual reports. The data collected is accessible and has been published on the official website of the Indonesia Stock Exchange and the official websites of each company. The observation period in this study is four years, namely 2021-2024.

3.4 Measures

Table 3.2 Research Variable Operations

Variable	Definition	Indicator	Scala	Source
Dependent variable				
Capital structure (Y)	A financing structure that includes long-term and short-term equity and liabilities.	$DER = \frac{\text{Total Debt}}{\text{Total Equity}}$	Ratio	M. Ahmed et al. (2024)
Independent variables				
Liquidity (X1)	The company's ability to pay off maturing short-term obligations.	$\text{Current ratio} = \frac{\text{Current assets}}{\text{Current liabilities}}$	Ratio	Boumlik et al. (2025)
Sales growth (X2)	Year-over-year sales changes that show sales movements in business activities.	$\text{Sales growth} = \frac{\text{Sales}_{(t)} - \text{Sales}_{(t-1)}}{\text{Sales}_{(t-1)}}$	Ratio	Cahya et al. (2021)
Tangibility (X3)	The proportion of fixed assets in the composition of the company's wealth used by the company as collateral.	$\text{Tangibility} = \frac{\text{Fixed assets}}{\text{Total assets}}$	Ratio	Albart et al. (2020)
Moderating variable				
Firm size (Z)	The size of a company, which indicates the amount of wealth it possesses.	Firm size = Ln total assets	Ratio	Gunardi et al. (2020)
Control variable				
Firm age (C1)	The age of a company indicates how long it has been operating since its establishment.	Company age = number of years since the company was founded.	Ratio	Saif-Alyousfi et al. (2020)

Source: Data processed by the author (2025)

3.5 Data Analysis

Data analysis is conducted after data collection to identify, measure, and understand the variations found in a set of variables (Hair et al., 2019). In data analysis, hypothesis testing is conducted to determine its validity based on statistical results (Bougie & Sekaran, 2021). In this study, the analysis technique

used multiple linear regression analysis with the help of the Stata 17 program. The techniques used ranged from outlier identification, descriptive statistical analysis, classical assumption testing, multiple linear regression analysis, regression model selection, hypothesis testing, and robust testing.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Identification outlier

Prior to conducting the regression analysis, a data quality assessment was performed to ensure that all observations met the basic assumptions of the model and did not contain values that could distort the estimation results. One important step in this process was the identification of outliers, defined as observations that deviate significantly from the general pattern of the data. The presence of outliers may affect the stability of regression coefficients and reduce the validity of the research findings.

Based on the results of statistics and data distribution analysis, extreme values (outliers) were identified in the capital structure and liquidity variables. These were indicated by a substantial gap between the minimum and maximum values relative to the mean, as well as noticeable dispersion within the data distribution. Therefore, this study applied a trimming method by excluding observations that fell outside the reasonable bounds of the distribution, in order to obtain more stable and representative estimation results.

Table 4.1 Statistic and Data Distribution

	Before Trimming				After Trimming			
	DER (Y)		LIK (X1)		DER (Y)		LIK (X1)	
	Percentil	Smallest	Percentil	Smallest	Percentil	Smallest	Percentil	Smallest
1%	-20,949	-34,93	0,012	0,000	-2,755	-14,670	0,032	0,119
5%	-1,004	-26,654	0,192	0,002	0,023	-4,129	0,213	0,015
10%	0,097	-20,949	0,253	0,119	0,119	-2,755	0,280	0,032
25%	0,416	-14,671	0,434	0,015	0,439	-1,010	0,446	0,043
50%	0,903		1,132		0,906		1,132	
		Largest		Largest		Largest		Largest
75%	2,171	8,621	1,944	25,397	2,146	6,939	1,938	14,385
90%	3,343	8,787	4,828	26,453	3,277	7,234	3,743	14,532
95%	5,587	14,750	7,597	54,613	5,153	8,621	7,078	25,397
99%	8,787	149,869	26,454	79,090	7,239	8,787	14,532	26,453
Std. Dev	10,926		7,104		2,015		3,229	

Source: Data processed by the author (2026)

The capital structure variable ranges from -34.93 to 149.87 with a standard deviation of 10.926, indicating extreme values and high data variation. Meanwhile, the liquidity variable ranges from 0.012 to 79.090 with a standard deviation of 7.104, indicating extreme values and fairly high data variation, thus requiring outlier handling through trimming. Trimming was performed at the 1% upper and lower levels of the distribution, because the extreme observations were at both percentiles of the distribution. After trimming, the sample data, which previously consisted of 216 observations, became 207 observations. However, the data distribution became more stable, as seen from the lower standard deviation values, namely 2.015 for the capital structure variable and 3.229 for the liquidity variable.

4.2 Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistical analysis is used to provide an overview of data characteristics through measures of central tendency and dispersion, including the mean, median, minimum, maximum, and standard deviation for each data point.

Table 4.2 Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Variable	DER	lik	pp	tan	um	uk
Mean	1,326	1,985	0,204	0,328	33,944	23,605
Median	0,906	1,132	0,079	0,201	29	25,105
Min	-14,671	0,012	-1	0	4	9,941
Max	8,787	26,454	10,965	0,914	140	32,272
SD	2,015	3,230	1,059	0,296	21,895	5,400

Source: Data processed by the author (2026)

Based on Table 4.2, descriptive statistics from the research data show that the capital structure variable (DER), measured using the debt to equity ratio, has a mean of 1.326 and a median of 0.906, indicating that companies in the infrastructure sector tend to use slightly more debt than equity in their financing. The liquidity variable (lik), measured using the current ratio, has a mean of 1.985 and a median of 1.132, indicating that companies in the infrastructure sector have a fairly good ability to meet their short-term obligations. The sales growth variable (pp), measured using the change in sales value from the current year to the previous year, has a mean of 0.204 and a median of 0.079, indicating that companies in the infrastructure sector have relatively positive sales growth on average. The tangibility variable (tan), measured by the proportion of fixed assets to total assets, has a mean of 0.328 and a median of 0.201, indicating that companies in the infrastructure sector have relatively low fixed assets in proportion to their total assets. The company age variable (UM), which is used as a control variable, has a mean of 33.944 and a median of 29. This shows that most companies in the infrastructure sector have been operating for quite a long time. The company size variable (UK) as a moderating variable is measured using the natural logarithm of total assets. The statistical results show a mean of 23.605 with a median of 25.105, indicating that the average company in the infrastructure sector is a relatively large company.

4.3 Classical Assumption Test

Table 4.3 Multicollinearity test

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
uklik	3,37	0,2970
uk	2,49	0,4019
lik	2,43	0,4120
tan	1,32	0,758
uktan	1,22	0,8171
ukpp	1,20	0,8329
um	1,15	0,8664
pp	1,12	0,8956
Mean VIF	1,79	

Source: Data processed by the author (2026)

Based on the results of the multicollinearity test above, the average VIF value obtained was 1.79. This indicates a VIF value < 10 , which indicates that there are no multicollinearity issues in the research variables, so the model is suitable for further analysis.

Table 4.4 Heteroskedasticity test

Type test	Prob > chi2
Breusch-Pagan	0,0128

Source: Data processed by the author (2026)

Based on the Breusch-Pagan test, a Prob > chi2 value of 0.0128 was obtained, which is < 0.05 . This indicates the presence of heteroscedasticity in the regression model. To overcome this, Cluster Robust Standard Error (CRSE) was used. According to Huang & Li (2022), the use of CRSE can correct the problems of heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation, so that the inference of the regression coefficient becomes more reliable and the estimation results are valid even though there are violations of classical assumptions.

Table 4.5 Autocorrelation test

Type test	Prob > F
Wooldridge	0,0001

Source: Data processed by the author (2026)

Based on the autocorrelation test results, a Prob > F value of 0.0001 was obtained, which is < 0.05 . This indicates the presence of autocorrelation. Therefore, a correction method using Cluster Robust Standard Error (CRSE) is needed to correct the autocorrelation problem so that the estimation results are more reliable and valid even though there are violations of classical assumptions.

4.4 Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA)

Moderated Analysis Regression (MRA) was conducted by including interaction variables to determine the role of moderating variables, namely whether company size can strengthen or weaken the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables. The results obtained in the moderation regression analysis are as follows:

Table 4. 1 Moderation Regression Analysis

DER	Coefficients	Robust std. error	t	p-value
lik	-0,087*	0,052	-1,66	0,096
pp	0,115**	0,046	2,46	0,014
tan	-0,119	0,546	-0,22	0,828
um	0,011	0,009	1,29	0,199
uk	0,067	0,043	1,54	0,123
uklik	-0,099	0,021	-0,45	0,653
ukpp	0,001	0,007	0,26	0,795
uktan	-0,218**	0,111	-1,96	0,050
Constant	0,875	0,300	2,91	0,004

Notes: ***1%, ** 5%, * 10%

Source: Data processed by the author (2026)

Table 4.6 represents the results of moderation regression analysis when all independent variables are considered to be at their average values, then the DER value will be at a level of 0.875, assuming other variables are constant. This value indicates that infrastructure companies on average have a low level of capital structure. Furthermore, the regression results indicate that liquidity has a negative effect on capital structure, sales growth has a positive effect on capital structure, and firm size can moderate tangibility on capital structure. Meanwhile, other results show that there is no effect on capital structure and firm

size cannot moderate it.

4.5 Coefficient of Determination (R²)

The coefficient of determination is used to measure how much variability in the dependent variable can be explained by the independent variables in the regression model. The smaller the value of R², the more limited the ability of the independent variables to explain the variation in the dependent variable. The results of the coefficient of determination are shown as follows:

Table 4. 2 Coefficient of Determination

Observasi	R-squared	Prob > F
207	0,1387	0,0001

Source: Data processed by the author (2026)

The coefficient of determination value is shown in the R-squared column as 0.13872 or 13.87%. This value indicates that the ability of the independent variables to explain the dependent variables is low because it only explains 13.87%, while the other 86.13% is explained by other factors outside the research model.

4.6 Robustness test

Robustness testing was conducted to ensure the robustness of the research model and to prove the validity of the research findings. There are several ways to conduct robustness testing, including using different measurements (Husin & Pinjaman, 2024). This

study uses another measurement technique for the dependent variable by changing the Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) to the Debt to Assets Ratio (DAR), which is often used as an indicator of capital structure in studies by Boshnak (2025); Chandra et al. (2022); Czerwonka & Jaworski (2021); Kuč & Kaličanin (2021); Marimuthu et al. (2023).

Table 4. 8 Robustness test

DAR	Koefisien	Robust std. error	t	P > t
lik	-0,731*	0,415	-1,76	0,078
pp	-2,257***	0,467	-4,80	0,000
tan	-15,940*	8,278	-1,93	0,054
um	0,019	0,506	0,38	0,706
uk	-1,467*	2,934	-1,70	0,089
uklik	0,303*	0,174	1,74	0,083
ukpp	0,793***	0,154	5,14	0,000
uktan	6,041**	2,934	2,06	0,040
Constant	4,514	3,417	1,32	0,186

Notes: ***1%, ** 5%, * 10%

Source: Data processed by the author (2026)

The robust test results show differences in results with the main regression model where when all independent variables are considered to be at their mean values, the average DAR value is predicted to be 4.514, which means that the company has a fairly high dominance of debt-financed assets. In addition, all variables have an influence and company size can moderate the relationship of all independent variables to the dependent variable. This difference in results occurs due to the different characteristics of DER and DAR in capturing the company's capital structure. DER is considered more sensitive because under certain conditions, such as company losses or capital deficiency, the amount of equity can change significantly to negative. Conversely, DAR reflects a relatively more stable asset funding structure because it uses total assets, which generally always have a positive value.

4.7 Discussion

4.7.1 Effect of Liquidity on Capital Structure

High company liquidity indicates the company's ability to pay short-term liabilities well, so that debt usage tends to decrease. In addition, strategically liquid companies reduce debt usage to maintain financial health (Alaali, 2025). The results of this study support the research of Alaali (2025), Gunardi et al. (2020), and Putri & Dwiarti (2024), which states that liquidity has a negative

effect on capital structure. These findings support the Pecking Order Theory, which states that companies tend to choose internal financing over external financing. Internal financing is considered to have a lower risk because it does not incur interest payments. In addition, internal financing has low information asymmetry costs and minimizes the financial risks that may arise from the use of debt.

4.7.2 Effect of Sales Growth on Capital Structure

Companies with higher sales growth tend to increase their use of debt in their financing structure. This condition reflects the company's need for additional funds to support operational expansion, increased production capacity, and greater working capital financing in line with increased sales activity. This finding is in line with the Trade Off Theory, which states that companies will balance the benefits and costs of using debt. Sales growth followed by effective cost management enables an increase in company profits. This condition can be a consideration for companies in determining their capital structure and taking advantage of the tax benefits arising from debt interest. This study is in line with research conducted by Cahya et al. (2021) and Pathak & Chandani, (2020), which states that sales growth has a positive effect on capital structure.

4.7.3 Effect of Tangibility on Capital Structure

In infrastructure companies, fixed assets such as heavy equipment, telecommunications networks, power plants, and transportation facilities have high value but do not generate direct cash flow and depend on utilization rates and market demand. In addition, most fixed assets are illiquid, making them less attractive as collateral for debt despite their high value. In Trade Off Theory, companies will balance the benefits of tax savings with the costs and risks arising from the use of debt. Fixed assets that have specific values, such as being difficult to transfer or resell, have the potential to increase bankruptcy costs when companies experience financial difficulties. Therefore, companies with high fixed assets tend not to significantly increase their use of debt. These findings support the research of Albart et al. (2020), Fitriyanto & Haryono (2020), and Hidayat et al. (2024), which states that tangibility does not affect capital structure.

4.7.4 Firm Size Moderates the Effect of Liquidity on Capital Structure

The results of this study are in line with the research by Gunardi et al. (2020), which states that company size cannot moderate the effect of liquidity on capital structure. Company size neither strengthens nor weakens the influence of liquidity in determining capital structure. This is because financing decisions are more influenced by liquidity, which reflects a company's internal funds, regardless of the size of the company according to the Pecking Order Theory. In this condition, both large and small companies will avoid using debt when internal funds are sufficient, so that differences in company size become irrelevant in influencing capital structure.

4.7.5 Firm Size Moderates the Effect of Sales Growth on Capital Structure

The results of this study are in line with the research by Renalya & Purwasih (2022), which states that company size cannot moderate the effect of sales growth on capital structure. According to Trade Off Theory, large companies tend to be better at balancing the tax benefits of using debt and the ease of obtaining loans. However, in large companies, operational assets are generally already available, so that sales growth does not always necessitate the addition of assets or business expansion that requires external funding, such as debt. In unfavorable conditions given this funding requirement, the company's

operational activities can be financed through internal funds, so that the company is not compelled to increase its debt.

4.7.6 Firm Size Moderates the Effect of Tangibility on Capital Structure

The results of this study are in line with the research by Fitriyanto & Haryono (2020) and Mukaromah & Suwarti (2022), which states that company size can moderate the effect of tangibility on capital structure. These findings show that in larger companies, fixed assets are no longer a major factor in borrowing, although in small and medium-sized companies, fixed assets are key assets that are pledged to obtain loans. However, in large companies, fixed assets are not the only consideration in borrowing decisions because financing decisions are more influenced by project portfolios, investment risks, growth strategies, and capital market conditions. The Trade Off Theory is relevant to small and medium-sized companies, where tangibility is a risk factor in the use of debt. Meanwhile, in large companies, the addition of tangibility is no longer significant in reducing risk because risk can be mitigated by other factors, so that the influence of tangibility on capital structure decreases as the company grows.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The findings of this study provide empirical evidence on internal factors that can influence a company's capital structure, especially infrastructure companies. Specifically, liquidity was found to have a negative and significant effect on capital structure, while sales growth had a positive and significant effect on capital structure, regardless of the size of the company. In addition, tangibility has a stronger influence on the capital structure of small companies because fixed assets are still key assets that are used as collateral to obtain loans due to their reputation and credibility, which are not as good as those of large companies. These results emphasize the importance of managing internal company factors in determining optimal capital structure policies, especially liquidity capacity, growth dynamics, and the company's asset structure.

5.1 Recommendations

While this study provides valuable insights, it has limitations. Further research is recommended to test the potential for endogeneity in order to obtain a more accurate causal relationship and minimize estimation bias due to simultaneity. In addition, the use of a longer observation period and expansion of the research object to other sectors is important to test the consistency of findings across different industry characteristics. Future studies may also consider adding other variables that could potentially influence capital structure decisions, including macroeconomic factors and other internal company factors, such as the use of additional moderating variables like profitability. Finally, the use of alternative proxies in measuring capital structure is recommended to test the robustness and consistency of results when measured with different indicators.

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